

This was written for the United Nations to take into for the development of all the nations among her membership states. It's a reality concept that could be adopted for all to enjoy and live a peaceable prosperous secured life in our changing world.

THE MANAGEMENT OF A NATION; AVOIDING PROTESTS, CHAOS AND WARS

(A Big Paradigm Shift; Seeing the Citizens as a Nuclear Family Member)

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INTRODUCTION

The epidemic happening around the world in various countries and nations has caused the urgent need of the management of nations and people to be a very challenging issue in this rapidly changing world, and this has given me a serious concern. Having studied the International Organisation Management with University of Geneva and with the United Nations as a case of study, this has given me great insights to the overview and the in-depth knowledge of this unsolved issue that leads to mismanagement of the people of a nation or country. This is why I call it an EPIDEMIC. It is viral from nation to nation, it's like people are forced to comply to rules, regulations and policies which are against human freedom in reality. They have no option but to migrate to other nations for survival and better life. These are reasons why people are not doing things willingly but because they have no choice, so they are comply forcefully to adapt but they're looking for opportunities to react, protest, fight and cause chaos which will eventually lead to war be it civil, national and international; Examples are the Syria, Ukraine, Russia etc.

If indeed we really want to disengage ourselves from what will lead to war both nationally and internationally, we must stop the mismanagement of people, we must look for ways to negotiate properly for security, economic stability, financial freedom, political stability and more beneficial innovations that will relief and make the citizens to trust their government both now and for their secured future.

This will lead to less pressure in the pursuit of achievements, safety, finance and survival as the case may be.

The need for the management of a nation; in avoidance of protests, chaos and wars will be explained in the texts, suggestions, recommendations and strategies will be given as a certified Management Consultant and Certified Management Specialist, that when follows after implementation is that the citizens of nations will be happy and see no reason for protests, chaos and wars both civil, nationally and internationally.

United Nations (UN) have got a serious challenging role to play in this issue, and to me, they are trying their best especially in the United Nations General Assembly with their different arms and agencies.

However, there are some countries that engage in the businesses of illegal arms trade international, who like wars in order to sell their war weapons, and make huge money from it. To such; wars are nothing as long as they are secure, mismanagement of a nation and all that will lead to wars; like protests, chaos, political instability etc., Will not be avoided because of their personal benefits from the war. As we have warlords, we also have drug lords. They work hand in hand and don't care what kind of chaos that will take place, as long as they will have their ways.

If the citizens are well taking care off with benefits in every aspect of their lives, this will minimize the rate of crimes, there will be less suicides, less pressure, protests will not even be the order of the day because right stakeholders are being consulted before taking the action of designing a policy for the benefits of all the citizens of that nation.

In fact, the government should see the citizens as nuclear family members that are bond by their culture, territorial area, language, common goals, etc., Thus, each citizen will give back to the society, what the society gives them, be it pain, struggle, hustle, pressure, hardship, benefits etc., This is my school of thought and my belief system, having observed critically what is happening in the society and around the world generally.

Does the government make her people happier? Hopeful and Safe in every area of their lives Or does the government leadership act as a dictator to enforce what is on their mindset against the citizens they governs and leads? Leaving the citizens to struggle on their own without the benefits from the government. This has been on my mind over eight months to write, to suggest and to recommend these views that will help the leadership of any nation or country that shows more concern to her people to make them happier when implemented. The nation will be valued by her citizens and loved. There will be peace, harmony and tranquility in their territory. In this way, most of the citizens will bring their positional ideas and insights for the growth of the nation's economy and safety and to go the extra mile for making policies that will make their nation to become the best of the best in all ramifications among the nations of the world.

THE ART AND ACT OF NATION'S MANAGEMENT & SAFETY FROM ABJECT POVERTY

The primary goals of a nation; deals with the basic needs of being together as a nation for provision and protection for each citizen of the country both in the resident places and every other place on the planet! Food, Shelter, Security in all dimensions and in every aspect of life.

The secondary goals of a nation; This is the fulfilment of the economic growth, sustainment of the citizens in form of education, health, employment, financial stability, infastructures, effective transportation systems, air, road, water, underground etc.,

The tertiary goals of a nation; This deals with international issues as related to the international communities, international trades, acceptability, mobility, exchange rate, power of access to other nations, tourism attractions etc.,

Then why protests? chaos? wars?... If things are done properly, amicably and diplomatically in the international scene with other nations.

Do we really need the army? Yes or No

If yes, who are we going to fight or is for defense of our citizens. Do we use our police or military to oppress and depress our citizens opinions. Is this not a slavery within our systems in the same nation that ought to provide for us, food, shelter, health, comfort, security etc., and protect us from danger, abuses of any kind from within our country and from outside our territory. Who wants to invade our systems, people, land and territory? We need to guide and guard ourselves. This is why we have our government to work for us. Never to enslave or oppress us as a citizen and as valuable people.

THE BIG SHIFT!

There is a big shift from physical invasion to intellectual, economical, territorial etc. both in a formal way which is direct and informal ways which is indirect methods of colonization in civilization. You can know these through population, economy, education, business, financial instability and the currency power in the international market.

The consequences of these will be seen by;

Willing Slavery; people decide, come what may, due to the lack, poverty and survival, that they will go as illegal immigrants to work in another country in search of food, good pastures, safety etc.,

Forceful Slavery; These are human trafficking, kidnapping, illegal labour migration, under pay for workers, etc.,

Educational Slavery; This deals with brainwashing to delete your philosophy and ideology in order to gain a certificate and embracing another new philosophy be it positive or negative. Your educational studies in your nation for certificates can not be used to work in a foreign land unless for the medicals, such as Nurses, Medical Doctors and some lecturing works in some countries.

Financial Slavery; This deals with other nations and determines the rate and power of your currency exchange at the international market. Who determines your nation's financial power?. This has also led to Migration of labour to other nations with a more powerful currency and higher exchange value.

Cultural Slavery; This strategy makes many to abandon their cultural heritage to speak and dress like another people and to adopt their cultures and lifestyle.

Economical Slavery; This deals with a nation imposing their laws and policies on another country's citizen's businesses, and the government can't respond and defend their citizens. This is happening in this 21st century and it's unimaginable!

How many British do come to your country now? What about the Americans? How many of them want to live in your nation? What about the Europeans? The Saudi Arabians? Except for some reasons like businesses, the gospel purpose, educational research, press, leadership conferences, big projects, summits and afterwards, off they go back to their countries because of the Infastructures, security measures are in place, everyone has equal rights in the face of the law. Is that the case in other nations?

Now, how many of your citizens wants to live and work in the western world? because there are infastructures, benefits,good roads, health treatment, housing, constant electricity, good educational systems, political stability, security,etc.,

Values are placed so much on their citizens that leads to provisions made available for all and protection for all.This is vital now!

Every government should place more value on their citizens and the results of this is to give them benefits and good things that will make life easier for them to live in their nation. In addition, this will be the job, the responsibility of a responsible leadership government of the 21century which I called the art and the act of managing a nation successfully without protests, chaos and wars.

Let the government see everyone in the nation and take the citizens as their own nuclear family members.The Babies, Children, Teenagers,Youths, Adults,the Elderly, Orphans etc., should be properly care for, always in every aspects of their needs. Such as food bank for the hunger, free accomodation, clean water, employment, uninterrupted electricity power supply, free education for all in all levels; from Primary School to University education in all Degrees, Training and Development, moral integration, citizens integration of rights and better life, peaceful environment,free Heathcare without condition, best infastructures. It will give the citizens self esteem, hope , secured future. Thus, they can go extra miles to support their government and nation.Through these concepts, you can govern a nation effectively and efficiently without protests, chaos and wars.

WHAT TYPES OF GOVERNMENT STYLE WILL BE BETTER TO USE?

The people of the nation will have to choose.A nation is a group of people with common goals and are bond with an agreed document for their laws, policies and procedures of doing things etc.,

What are the reasons of using such government style of approach? Who and what are the primary target which are the citizens welfare, what are the stick-yard measurements and who determines how to go about the government; the citizens or the leader that served them? These must be clearly stated and solved.

We have; A. Autocratic leadership style

B. Democratic leadership style

- C. Parliamentary system of government
- D. Presidential system of government
- E. Monarch system of government
- F. Theocracy system government
- G. Communism system of government
- H. Aristocracy system of government
- I. Colonialism system of government
- J. Socialism system of government
- K. Oligarchy system of government etc.,

Monarch plus Democracy? Can we combine two or three systems of government style in order to achieve the best results. Yes, of course, Examples are; Spain, Netherland, France, United Kingdom, Saudi Arabia, etc., why using two systems of government in one nation? All is because of check and balance! This has being of a great help to their nations and their environment including their neighbouring countries.

A king or A Queen will not want his or her Kingdom and nation to collapse, or destroy by any means. Of course, the cultural heritage will be protected in the mist of the civilization. More caution and precaution will be taken into consideration, consultation will be made both from the stakeholders, and the policy makers before designing any policy for the citizens to follow.

Therefore, A, B, C, D, E, F of leadership styles and government can be mixed up, for better performance and productive if the need be.

However, this have to be agreed upon by the citizens, the governed, as the case may arises so that it will not cause, protests, chaos and wars.

It is necessary to develop a nation strategy. Underdeveloped nations and developing nations has a lot to do as regard to these developments. It high time to work deliberately for the growth of your nation as a leader in the government.

The government owns the majority of the responsibility should anything is not working, that is why you are called a leader and the leadership must be accountable for any mismanagement, protests, chaos and wars. The political stability and economical stability will enhance quality continuity growth, quality life, in every aspects, sectors, and sections of the nation and the government.

God created us to live in love, harmony, peace and tranquility. This must be maintained and managed by and government for her citizens.

DEFINITION OF ABJECT POVERTY BASED ON THE UNITED NATIONS

Based on the United Nations. What is Abject poverty? and why? In the cause of this writing, I will like you to know and see how people are suffering in their own nations. Where will they migrate to? Is it to become an illegal immigrants, refugees, looking for hope, do you know the implications of your actions as a government if you do not rise to your being responsible to your responsibilities? Many lives, who are the citizens of your country are suffering and you are enjoying. The law of karma is effective and naturally will take its place one day. This is a challenge to every leadership in government to endeavour that the citizens are taking as a nuclear family members with dignity and responsibility for becoming greater nation that is well to live in.

It's high time for a mandate to be given by the United Nations for every developing nations to rise in development for their nations to become a developed nations at all cost despite their sovereign status. Examples are; Singapore, Hong Kong, UAE, South Korea, etc.,

According to the United Nations, Abject Poverty also have various names, like, Extreme poverty, Deep poverty, Absolute poverty, Destitute or Penury which is the most severe type of poverty define by the United Nations (UN) as a condition characterized by **SEVERE DEPRIVATION OF BASIC HUMAN NEEDS**, these includes;

Food

Safe Drinking Water

Sanitation Facility

Health

Shelter

Education and

Information.

The above depends not only on income but also on access to SERVICES"

(UN 1995 report of the World Summit for Social Development) Historically, other definitions have been proposed within the United Nations.

The standard of living matters, basic needs of life is necessary for human to be comfortable. This means values are attached to human, the severe deprivation of basic human needs are threats to the world, humanity, the nation and the citizens in every country except the rich.

In fact, if care is not taken the rich are not secure in some places because hunger, frustration can lead to misbehaving of people, bad gang, terrorist etc., because the penury people may see that there are no

reason for them to live in the world. When the fellow human being like them are enjoying in the other nations or part of the world. This may cause them for being violence, doing chaos things, protest violently and opposing the tranquility of the nation. All they want is war because they were frustrated, and want to destroy everything. It is high time for the United Nations to respond quickly to this concepts by engaging her 187 States Members in the General Assembly on what to do in order to advert the consequences of having extremely poverty in any nation, else, the damage it would bring on humanity and the world at large could make life difficult to live in for others these are part of the world problems.

People should have access to information,health, education, shelter,food,clean water, sanitation facility and good environment; like good road, effective transportation system, communication etc.,

THE UNITED NATIONS PROGRAMS FOR THE 187 MEMBERSHIP STATES

United Nations have got the vision to care for individual on the earth as a family members, other nations must emback on free programs and benefits for all their citizens. This will help to achieve the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) towards 2030.

The United Nations is trying her best,to create more programs for the world.Like Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) and now. The 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) target to end extreme poverty in 2030.

However,if the other nations leadership do not comply with these measure standards of development. It will lead to uncertainty in some corner of the world. When people are educated, trained, enlightened and exposed. The way they act varries from those who had not been trained be it formal or informal. Every government have to work very hard to manage thier nations before war break up. Anything that the leadership could do to avoid, protests, chaos and wars should be done quickly.

We need to be proactive as a nation builder not a nation destroyer.For this reason,why should a reasonable nation emback on war when you know that war will destroy things, living and non living, infastructures, genocide,hunger,dismay,fear, vandalization, robbery, women abuse,child mortality, displacement, desolation. Afterward, trauma,bad experience,etc,. We have to discourage war. Some people and nations are benefiting from it, as a business but at the expenses of others; wastage of valuable lives. Is this the world we are meant to live in ? At the end of the day, the countries where the war took place will be given the United Nations a great unending challenges and huge tasks to solve. The puzzle will be very difficult to solve for the United Nations. Are they going to building infastructures? Industries that have been destroyed by the war, can the death rate be reverted ? In war both parties suffers, one way or the other, only that one may be much in casualty than the other nation. Every government must avoid war.

The United Nations are doing great works, the international communities, international organizations,the World Bank, international labour organization etc.,

As of 2018, It is estimated that the country with most people living in extreme poverty is Nigeria at 86million people!

Vast majority are in South Asia and Sub-Saharan Africa. The International poverty line is minimum spending of \$1.90 a day! Equivalent to \$1.00 a day 1996 US price. Therefore, extreme poverty as an income below the international poverty line.

In view of this, the government of every nation must stop mismanagement, corruption of deeds, characters, diversion of national resources to personal pockets. Let there be proper accountability and transparency in the administration of the national funds, and resources for the benefits of all the citizens. These will help to eradicate poverty, mentally, financially through unemployment and the basic human needs should be given free to the citizens that lacks in their nation as a bond family precious citizens.

POVERTY THRESHOLD

This is another insights that will help the readers to understand the danger of the government not taking care of the citizens as supposed. The level of poverty varies from one nation to the other and from the look of things, once the family couldn't take care of the members, the government have to come in because they are the hope of the masses. Else, if care is not taken to put the right measures in place, frustrated people will rob in broad daylight, hunger, anger etc., can turn people's behavior to something different. This may lead to catastrophe at the end of the day, is a matter of time.

The Poverty Threshold, Poverty limit, Poverty line or Breadline is the minimum levels of income deemed adequate in a particular country.

When inflation rate goes up, it is necessary for the government to strategize ways of increasing workers basic salary and allowances so that the incomes will be able to meet up with living expenses. If this is not done, the government want to create protests and chaos.

Poverty line is usually calculated by finding the total cost of all essential resources that an average human adult consumes in one year. The largest of this expense is typically the RENT required for accomodation, so historically, Economists have paid particular attention to the REAL ESTATE MARKET and HOUSING PRICE as a strong poverty line effects. Individual factors are often used to account for various circumstances, such as wether one is a parent, elderly, a child, married, single mother, etc., The Poverty Threshold maybe adjusted annually as things change especially the economy growth or economic instability. Are the people employment ? What is their avarage salary, allowances etc., can have impacts on their poverty threshold.

In real sense, if the government will help the citizens for accomodation like in United Kingdom, you will see that the level of the Poverty Threshold will reduce and can be eradicated completely. When the leadership in government see the citizens as her nuclear family members. Every focus, strategies, policies, regulations, laws, etc., will be to benefits the citizens and make them more happier and loved, unity support, development, progress, prosperity etc., will be the rewards of the day with positive

thinking. In my own view, when your citizens are extremely poor the government and the nation are also extremely poor both physically, mentally, financially, educationally etc., because the government is the people!

THE POVERTY LINE IN THE DEVELOPED NATIONS AND DEVELOPING NATIONS

In practice, like the definition of poverty, the official or common understanding, the POVERTY LINE is significantly higher in the developed countries than the developing countries. Why most of the developed nations things are expensive, to live there, work, settled bills, such as house rent, transportation, gas, establishing businesses are very expensive as compared to the developing nations who's labour are cheaper. So when a worker is fired in the workplace, the employee become unemployed and will not be able to maintain the standard luxury apartments or home. The effects will be much than you can ever imagine.

To this, I felt it is more than necessary for the government of both developing nations and developed nations to assist the citizens if in deed they will see them as their nuclear family members. It will not be a concept of helping or assisting the citizens but the government in leadership will see and act on being responsible for doing what should be done, as part of her responsibility to make sure every citizens are provided for because they have value, we are one big family in this nation. What a life of honouring the citizens, the harvest of this will help the society to become a more better place to live. This will attract the people in other nations to come and settled in such an environment better than how their government have being governing them without right direction of purpose. This a good war of competition; it's warfare packages, welfare standard of living etc., This will be the next phase of better life, better country that is the champion league. No more DESTRUCTION of infrastructures, lives, properties but DISTRIBUTION of wealth, hope, benefits, love, kindness etc., this will definitely create an atmosphere and environment of more trust and responsible government with people.

In October 2015, the World Bank updated the INTERNATIONAL POVERTY LINE (IPL) a global absolute minimum, to \$1.90 per day.

By measure of this, the percentage of the global population living in absolute poverty fell from 80% in 1800 to 10% by 2015 according to the United Nations estimates which roughly about 734 million people remain in absolute poverty around the World. There are hope, changes but we can do better in this 21st century if all nations mean the business of placing more values on all their citizens.

MORE UNDERSTANDING FOR SOCIAL RESPONSIBILITY BY ABLE INDIVIDUAL AND CORPORATE BODY!

Therefore, for us to deal with this issue and tackle it very fast for a better life in our World. There must be a love for Individual Social Responsibility and Cooperate Social Responsibility.

Why do you say you are the richest man on earth and in your nation? I do not believe that you are rich, as long as part of your nuclear family members are in abject poverty. It means you're still very poor with your wealth. This is why you as a rich and wealthy person in the nation have to make sure that the wealth is distributed to all the citizens. During the lockdown, many things were discovered, who is who? Where is your money? People who have the mindset of social responsibility culture, helped their neighbouring people. Some governments have to respond positively.

The United Nations did a very wonderful work and many others. While there are some people who used that means to make themselves richer by that medium, they took advantage of the systems and the grant to do leverage for their companies, etc.,

A lady told me how she single handedly gave food stuffs to everyone in the houses in her street. I was profound! No one enforced her to do that, she has a concept of family, love and she extended it to others.

The Richest man in Africa, America, Asia, Australia, Europe, etc., look critically to your country people who had no houses, food, etc., You will have to do more so that you can be remembered for good. It's out of love for you, as an individual to engage in social responsibility. If you discovered that the leadership of your country or nation are not performing, build an estate with moderate houses, tell people to come and live there freely. Build a free University for all both undergraduate degree and post-graduate studies. Especially, in the developing nations and some developed nations. The masses will enjoy your wealth with you, by so doing the society will get back what they give the people!

In America, I learnt that the former president, Donald Trump gave the American money from his own pocket, that is an individual social responsibility. What a wonderful care for his country people. I believe many other people, great and small helped in one way and the other. Today, the lockdown is gone and we are all surviving, getting our feet back to re-organized ourselves better for a hopeful life. Really, many are gone, may their souls rest in perfect peace and may the Almighty comfort every family that have lost member (s) in the lockdown and the covid 19 issues.

Furthermore, on the issue of social responsibility, it is essential that the corporate social responsibility becomes a policy for huge companies. I am aware that some are doing their social responsibility on their environment but we have to do more in order to eradicate the extreme poverty. Every company exists because of people and they gain from the masses. It will be very good to reward the rest citizens which I will not like to use the word the common people because there should be valued as living things. It is this value that can propel us and inspire us to look at their welfare. No one should be in extreme or abject poverty should be our targeted goal as a responsible nation and responsible government.

Personally, had seen a family man walked to me that he is married, no place to stay for the wife and their children. This was more than 20 years ago. Out of what I had, we have to give and later mobilize our organization and we paid for him to have accommodation. The same goes for a newly married couple I had to get them accommodation. When we do not do a corporate benefits and the people were frustrated

they end up vandalized the company we built one day, when there are protest,chaos and wars. Individually and as a corporate body we should engage in social responsibility on daily basis. Especially the international organizations. It will be very good for the government to engage, collaborate and associate with this organizations for more impacts on the citizens lives.

THE WESTERN WORLD GOT THE VISION!

Most people are coming from all over the world into the Western world especially the United Kingdom due to the free health programs, free accomodations and free education to the High school levels and their Universities loan system.

So many of the European Union study for free for their education, from primary to doctorate levels as you desires, couple with their free hospital treatment, free delivery for pregnant women, etc.,some allowance for the parents, spendit for some higher levels education for encouragement etc.,these are benefits.

It cost the government a serious huge budgets but that is how your leadership have shown the world, how to govern and lead well. This means that as a citizen you are all entitled to being taken proper care of your life, through provisions for sustainable development and protections for secured life from your government.

UNITED ARAB EMIRATES (UAE) GOT THE VISION MORE!

Recently, the United Arabs Emirates (UAE) have caught the vision for her citizens to be more happer. For example, free education for all to the University level and to study abroad which their government will be responsible for all the payment, free healthcare and surgery of any kind, \$20,000Dollars for newly Weds couple, free land to build house for the couple,and interest free loan for the building of the house, fee healthcare for the elderly, free funeral, etc., these benefits will make their people to relax, and love their nation more than any nation on the planet!

The pressure of living a standard life will be lesser because citizens needs and desires of wants are meet.Especially,the basics and the advanced need for standard life are dealth with. Of course,it will cost the government huge money but all these will help the citizens to repay the society what was done for them. Why should someone steal? If the government will fund the education to University level,even to any level of degrees. Such a fellow will put back the acquired knowledge and strategies to help the society and the country for better growth and development.

A NATION WILL GET THE VISION TO CARE FOR HER CITIZENS BETTER THAN ALL!

We are waiting to see the model of models, who will show case to the world how to run a nation as a family members. This conceptual thought of the management of a nation; avoiding protests, chaos and wars will help to resolve every unsolved issue in a country for the betterments of our world.

This should be a competition among the nations to know who is who, not as a world power but as a nation that non of her citizens lacks anything; this type of goals and vision will place more value on humans, practically speaking in word and deeds than anything else. Thus, the migration towards a better pastures will be controlled willingly because when every nations emback on providing for her citizens adequately, making them more comfortable in standard of living, the issue of human trafficking, children abuse, women abuse, illegal immigrants, crossing the Mediterranean sea which is a suicide and criminality of many kinds will be limited to zero degree.

Infact, in some of the western world, there are some people that lacks home, employment, University education despite the opportunities that are there because there are some policies that do not engage the citizens as a FAMILY MEMBER for full free total welfare!

I think this should be discussed in detail in the UN General Assembly and will be helpful for achieving the United Nations 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) towards 2030.

This proposal will enhance infastructures, financial stability, marital emotional support, political stability, security of properties and reduction of casualty of any kind. When there are too much pressure under inflation, many things will come to mind of people such as frustration, misbehaving, bad intentions, killing, lack of value for humanity, marriage, home, property, government and their systems of operations etc., Are we not surprised to see and heard a suicide bomber? All because the vulnerable people thought that there are no reason to live, while others have good engagement with life blossoming, comfortable and focuses on integration of a better ideas and business in the society and developmental growths.

The opposite was the case of some, due to their bad environment, backgrounds, lack of education and oppressive systems from their nation's corrupt leadership and governorship. When we mention corruption; it means a lots! corruption in deeds, words, fake promises to the citizens, oppression which will lead the citizens for depression, whereas, depression can cause citizens to protests, engage in chaos which we lead to political instability followed by wars.

In this age, with the help of the United Nations and all the international organizations as an arms, agencies and their supports for humanity. The world don't need a nation that will win a war but the one that will care for the world are the nations we need presently. In making life easier for the children of today that turn to become the youth of tomorrow, the women should be proud of the country they are for inequality in employment, government and in other areas of life. The fulfilment of the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) 2030. To make life easier for all either rich or poor. It's time to share the burdens and help one another as a nation to nation, as a government to her citizens. Through this, there will be great unity in every works of life in the nation because the leadership of the nation is after the WELFARE OF HER CITIZENS NOT WARFARE OF DISTRUCTION of whatever we had built over the years.

These and many more will grow the development of the nation both in mentality and facility for today's generation and that to come.

THE DEVELOPING NATIONS AND DEVELOPED NATIONS

THE DEVELOPING NATIONS

Most of the developing nations have a lot of work to do because they have natural resources, some have not be tapped into, while some that have been discovered are not well utilized and maximized. The government should engage, collaborate and associate with the other nations that are taking proper care of their citizens. Information can be shared, provisions of strategies and sustainable methodology could be given, if the willingness is there, from the government leadership to enhance their citizens for mass benefits for all.

Every corrupt government should be investigated and put to order because the rate at which development and management of the developing nations are handling infastructures, free educational systems, political stability and security measures are no where to be found in this 21st century.

All the developing nations must be serious and emback on massive restructure and should take their citizens as their family members in the management of their nation in oder for them to avoid protests, chaos and wars without using a forceful method through the military and the police.

I think despite the sovereign of the developing countries as a nation, the other government leaders can speak with love to their counterpart presidents on how to help the citizens,the methods and strategies of the right policies should be shared to help each nation among the United Nation membership states.

It's unimaginable on how some roads are not fixed in most of the developing countries.Light is a big problem for without it,many development will be hindered and life will be difficult for business, industries, manufacturing, domestic life, hospitals,etc., In this 21st century,every nations that are developing countries should do more to become developed. We all can see how United Arab Emirate(UAE) capital Dubai, started and today have become a tourist attractions,with their effective transportation, especially,their Emirates flight and other infastructures. All because it's a deliberate deliveryand transparency in the government. There are targeted goals with a deadline line of achievements. This should challenge every other developing nations to rise to work for prosperity and economic impact for overall national purpose.

ENOUGH IS ENOUGH!

The United Nations should utilized their position in influencing the General Assembly that her 187 Membership States should impliment drastic actions for proper policies and procedures that will

catering for the citizens of each nation among the United Nations with greater supervision and under cover intelligents to ask from the citizens, from the common people in the streets and to the local communities. With this method, the truth identification of events, standard living, and what the government is doing will be revealed than a falsehood report from any quarters. This is a suggestion in my opinion to safeguard the poor masses from messes across the globe.

The budget on refugees protection, provisions and adaptation is so enormous that if we can avoid wars, chaos etc., The United Nations can focus and use the budgets on impacting welfare for all. The trumer that an individual and a nation experience may not leave the person for the rest of his or her life after the war. Those nations that engage in war arms, weapons and the machinery who are warlords. How long do we as a family member of the United Nations? Accept this ironic views and business strategies that are killing, genocide, hunger, rape of women, the elderly, children, vulnerable and victims of the wars etc., What a terrible life? we are living. Meanwhile, the big business people behind the close doors are enjoying the profit-sharing from the wars. I think is high time to re-think our decisions towards right living, human value, nations social and economic stability for greater tomorrow.

THE DEVELOPED NATIONS

The developed nations have get some insights into this phenomenon but not all of them have actually emback in helping their citizens for all these free benefits. What is really happening? Is it lust of power, self-esteem or what? that we are seeing some people in the develop nations sleeping on the street. This is unacceptable. Why can't we get the insights that we are one big family as a nation. It's high time to structure development and the management of the lives of our fellow citizens by the government.

Many people are dying in silence due to traumatic experience and depressive thoughts. It's my desire that the United Nations will have to persuade and encourage all the 187 Membership States to do more for their citizens for comfortable secured life. This will help humanity to some extent.

The pains of self struggling and hustling has made most people to react negative in their dealings on daily basis. This is a huge big work. In the mist of these errors and pervert. We have to correct and re-adjust the nation's programs and policies that will be helpful and productful to all the citizens.

In the developed nations; more is expected from the government by the citizens because in terms of population growth, more work need to be done. The policy makers must seek to know what their people need and want, that will help the government to administer what will be acceptable by the people.

It's high time for the developed nations to be of more examples in transparency, diplomacy and democracy to the developing countries. As no one is above the law in the developed nations, so it must be in the developing countries. leaders who vioate the laws should not be watch by the United Nations but should be brought to book. This discipline will help to fulfill the target of transforming the whole nations in the world. The warlords, dealers in war ammunition should not create wars for the purpose of selling and making profits.

Meanwhile, the United Nations seek for funds to take care of the refugees, red cross, civil-military operations coordination for safety. All these can be avoided when we are after welfare not warfare. The consequences of wars are unlimited. It's time in pursuing peace, harmony than international trades for the destruction of humanity. This underground businesses that is against peace but create more problem for the world must be stopped by the General Assembly and the Security Council of the United Nations.

THE DEFINITIONS AND SOME TERMINOLOGY

According to Longman Active Study and Contemporary English Dictionary on the subjects of discussion the definitions of my terms are;

MANAGEMENT; The job of control and organising the work of a company or organization. That is to say, the planing, directing, coordinating, distributing, implimenting and controlling the resources of a nation towards the national goals or interest of the citizens.

NATION; A politically independent country; this is a sovereign nation that have a capacity and recorgised by the world to govern herself without any interfarrance.

CITIZENS; Someone who have a legal rights to live and work in a particular country either by birth or by documentation.

GOVERNMENT; The group of people who govern a country and the process of governing a country. They are powerful and purposeful. They design the structural ways and policies of doing things as agreed in an accepted document.

LEADERSHIP; The quality of being good at leading a team , organization, or country. People who are in charge of a country. They can be called the government because they are in charge of the nation to provide and to protect their citizens.

STAKEHOLDERS; Someone that have important connection with someone. These are the citizens or their representatives that work with the leadership of the nation to achieve the objectives and common goals of their country.

POLICIES; a way of doing something that have been officially agreed and chosen by a political party, business or organization. The policies become a regulations, laws and mandate ones it is signed into

a bill, it's becomes a binding documents that must be obeyed and followed by everyone that are in the country be it the citizens or foreigners.

STRUCTURE;The way in which the part of something are connected with each other to form a whole.These are the departmental and sectorial part of the nation, that when bringing together forms the total shape of how the nation operation their government and all their activities within the national system and international.

DEVELOPMENT;The process of gradually becoming bigger,better,stronger or more advanced.

AVOIDING;To prevent something bad from happening, to deliberately not to do something especially something wrong, dangerously or harmful either to your nation or the citizens in their own understanding.

PROTEST; Something that you do, to show publicly that you think something is wrong and unfair.This can be in any form; noise, violence,while some go steadily without a fight but just to express their views by writing on papers, cardboard,plank, banners etc.,

CHAOS;A situation in which everything is happening in a confused way,and nothing is organized or arranged in order.

WAR;When their is fighting between two or more countries or between opposing groups within a country involving large numbers of soldiers and weapons.Moreso, a situation when person or group is fighting for power, influence or control.Wars are in various levels, tribal wars, religion wars,civil wars, nation and international.Whichever ways,protests, chaos and wars can be avoided by simple negotiate, engage the citizens in every policies and things you want to do,that is why I called them the stakeholders.

BENEFITS; An advantage, improvement or help that you get from the government, people or everyone want free things, especially when the hardship in an environment is too hard. The government can be of a great help to reduce the suffering encounter on daily basis by the citizens.

POLICYMAKERS;These are group of people that decide what an organization or government government will do and followed.For this reason,the lawmakers are the policymakers,it is necessary to carry everyone alone before making laws.If in deed they want it to be more effective.

The definition of the nuclear family according to the internet means a couple and their dependant children regarded as a basic social unit.This means that every citizens of any nation are dependants to their government for social secured life in all ramifications.

Whatever names or titles anyone bears as Honorable, President,Prime Ministers,State Governor or Mayor, Senator etc., We are meant to serve the citizens and to bring transformation to lives.This is a privilege of engagement that will be disengage as the term and years goes.

Therefore, the leadership and governorship should work as a team for better performance and accountance.The capitalist should be engaged to show the better way of economic productivity and

stability. Every bad mindset should be removed, enlightenment, love thinkers and welfare of the citizens should be the parameters for the order of the day. Negative philosophy should be eradicated for us to enjoy free nations without protests, chaos and wars. Why are we in the nation, and the world at large; is to help ourselves, love, unity, support, development and discoveries for better lives.

POLICYMAKERS AND STAKEHOLDERS

It is essential for every nation and international policymakers to have in-depth knowledge and broad overview of the international communities goals for their citizens welfare, standard life despite the increase in inflation.

The policymakers are the one that need to have human feelings most, before the designing of any policy in any sectors of the country, any region of the nation and in any arm of the government. The stakeholders must be met with full detailed knowledge, and awareness of the latest development, proper investigation must be done as a research to know and to use the best practical easy methods that is achievable in every strategical policy before implementations, else, the government of that nation is inviting protests and chaos. It is more than necessary for every government in any nation to improve on their goals and objectives to build human capacity development and human resources management. The totality of these capacity building will help the growth and the sustainable development of the nation which the leadership govern.

When there is political stability, security will be achieved and economic growth will take its place. Partnership from international organizations will evolve and the tranquility will attract investors. This will lead to the creativity of large corporations, international labour market for employment purpose and fulfilment.

The social development and benefits will enhance quality continuity lives for the citizens and the nation at large.

THE SIMPLE STRATEGICAL WAY TO AVOID PROTESTS, CHAOS AND WARS

PRODUCTIVE STRUCTURE

There must be right structure in place, for development programs, continue projects that will not stop after the term of anyone in the office of government. When everyone's interest is on the national issue.

Things will take shape. Love of citizens will bring the willingness and eagerness to render services that will be productive and attractive to each member of the nation.

POWER OF CONSISTENT MOTIVATION

It is necessary to always appreciate and motivate the citizens through charity works and benefits for free education to University level, free hospital treatment, free accommodations, free food bank, free access to the government and its leadership to communicate as a citizen without denials. This kind of encouragement, motivation, empowerment etc., will reduce insecurity, fear, injustice, etc., Then harmony will bring the positive impacts on the society at large. Suicide will be eradicated because people will be happy as their needs are being met.

Through these practical benefits, citizens will be loyal, contribute to the nation's development by adding their ideology and strategy. The benefits have a psychology positive impacts for love, care, concern without being abandoned by their immediate family and the government of their nation. This leads to some philosophy of life about being good to people and the repayment or do I say; the pay back time!

To the society and the nation by the way the citizens were been treated in their own country by their country men. This in deed will bring about how to invest back into the country when they had the opportunity to leave and taste another nation. This is one of the reasons why many people in the diaspora will not want to settle back in their original homeland, where there are no security, political instability, economic instability, lack of good infrastructures, bad transportation systems, fears and different unpredictable chaos. In life, the law of karma is one of the philosophy of life, what are the leadership in the government doing to their citizens? Are they oppressive, offensive, and depressive. The citizens in turn will repay and these will lead to the harvest of what the government had done for her precious citizens. I see that when the government take the citizens as their own nuclear family, the case will be different! When values are placed so much on the citizens, to engage, collaborate and associate with what will be beneficial to them all, it will be easier to achieved the national goals of the nation.. The focus will be caring not looting the treasury, there will be concern for the masses not abandon the people that makes a nation. The leadership of every nations are meant to served and lead for better productivity, longevity, sustainability and reliability.

SOLID TRANSPARENT AND CONTINUOUS COMMITMENT.

This is a great necessity for the growth of a nation no matter what, for transparency to be within the leadership, the government and the citizens for effective purposes in all the administration with the management of the nation.

The embankment of continuous commitment on every policies, projects, research, innovations and the evaluations with feedbacks will aid the achievement of the national goals.

This need is a major challenges in every nations that have being experiencing setbacks, instability of security, political instability, economic instability,the lacks of proper direction to fundings.When there is transparency in the government and it's leadership,the people comply easily to rules, regulations, policies,laws because they will see need for adaptation,hope for prosperity expecially when the policymakers carry them along as the stakeholders before designing of any policy for the nation.

Most leadership fail in the management of their nation due to the facts of relaxing because of achievements without knowing that, there are competitions among the nations of the earth. Competition? Oh yes, a very serious competitive market of management to become the best among other nations; in economics, power, standard of living, education, discoveries, development, infastructures, financial stability, in exchange rates, exports and imports of their international trades,self esteem for their international passport for easy access into other nations.

This Diplomatic relations within and among nations is the real diplomatic systems of benefits for the country and her citizens. It's a major concepts, futuristic visions,goals and objectives that a well meaningful government should understand with her team players for delivery an effective mandate to their citizens. For this reason, the citizens will trust their government and the leadership of their nation. In addition, the government must not relent in total commitment to keep the ball rolling because of the changes and the trends in the world at large on daily basis in Technology, Science, Medicals, Businesses, Education, Infastructures,arts, etc.,

ACTIONS ARE LOUDER THAN VOICE!

The power of positive behavioral therapy are beyond benefits of doubt. It is necessary that to be responsible as a leader in fulfilling your responsibility both in the private and public domain are predominantly the focus of everyone that should be in the government.The citizens want leadership that could manage them and their resources properly for esteems that they could be proud of both presently and hopefully in the nearest future.

In view of this, the citizens look for leaders, managers, statemens, president, governor, mayor, prime minister, senator, policies makers, etc.,that will manage their lives as a nation. The challenges of the 21st century is that people eyes are open than ever in a global world. The citizens are exposed, enlightened,educated and challenged to know what the government of their country were doing as compared to the development in other nations.

The comparison do not make the citizens to appreciate what their government are doing that are not outstanding and exceptionally beautifying in nature.Therefore, the interest of the nation must be the priority to individual values.

THE LAW OF KARMA

The law of karma state what ever you do, the consequences will return back to you. With this mindset and view, government should note that doing well for the citizens will promote unity, social advantage, growth and development, care and loving one another in respect with great caution in daily dealings on whatever contracts, projects and contacts for realization of the national dreams if indeed the leadership in the government are there not only for self gain and business profit making ventures as a godfather politicians.

GOVERNMENTAL AGENCIES

The government agencies must follow through and be more efficiently productive to the citizens, it's not a position to dominate but to served and give proper reports to the appropriate quarters for the development and management of the nation. If any precautions are not taken, this can lead to protests, chaos if proper measures are not in place, it can lead to war within the systems and affect the nation the government is building negatively.

Most nations especially, the developing countries should embrace detailed dialogue, negotiate, with the citizens before establishing their policies. The underdeveloping nations should partner with the nations that can help them in development, infrastructures and economic growth.

The purpose of each sectors in the country is to work towards the national goals. Moreover, the directions in achieving these objective are major work for the welfares of all the citizens from children to adults for the fulfilment of the primary goals as a nation.

PREVIEW AND REVIEW

It is necessary to review and preview the progressive achievements and to evaluate it, monthly, quarterly and annually for performance checking, tracking, adjusting etc., as the case maybe.

The campaign towards our goal as a nation and citizens is an important phenomenon that will give the individual in the nation; values, self esteem, hope, information, benefits and to know that they belong to the government and the nation as a whole.

- A. The Children
- B. The Youths
- C. The Women
- D. The Men

E. The Elderly

A,B,C,D,E are all citizens that benefits should be directed to them continuously with full commitment. Every government must endeavour to meet all their needs adequately both in the present and in the future. This will boost trust and it's a great honour to the nation that her citizens are living in joy with the resources of their nation both natural, artificial and the human capital.

THE BASIC NEED OF LIFE A IS A NECESSITY!

The basic needs of life is a necessity for every citizens to have by a responsible and a loveable government. This will put a limit on criminality, depression,short life expectancy,health issue, suicide, pressure,etc.What are these basic needs; food, shelter, clothing, security, employment etc.,

In this texts, am going to analyze and diagonise these needs to for major dimensions, namely;

1. MENTALITY
2. PROSPERITY
3. FACILITY
4. SECURITY

Under each of these four dimensions for development and management of a nation for us as a government to avoid, protests, chaos and wars. Am going to discuss on each of them so that you can see and know in details what we need to do for our citizens as a responsible parents will go the extra miles for the children to be comfortable. I believed the citizens should be taken as a children from your own bloodline for you to really understand the purpose of government and nation.

1. MENTALITY

Citizens mentality have to be taking proper care of,the need for right mindset, philosophy and the right historical events with the purposes about the nation existence.This will bring about the formulation of the educational systems that will enhance quality and continuity of training, exposure, enlightenment,that will shape responsible behavioral therapy for individual in the country.This must be free education for all in all levels because they are citizens.Thus, the understanding of the effects of protests and chaos that leads to war will be understood, for such image in the international communities does not proof a good governance and nation.

FREE EDUCATION FOR ALL IN ALL LEVELS!

Things must be handled properly and cautiously before escalating. To this, the citizens must be well educated, trained, enlightened and exposed not to do the harmful things that will affect the nation negatively, but that is when the government engage them as a stakeholders when designing every policies that will govern them with full responsibility and transparency.

THE PRISON

again, the prison should be a training grounds for discipline and rehabilitation centers, for corrective measures and not necessarily a punishment center. Most people that came out of prison became worsening especially in the developing nations and some developed nations because of the horrible things happening there everyday, the environment, the fear and the treatment. I repeat, that for us to have a better society and nation, corrective measures should be in love with a vision to place value on the citizens. The mindset is for the government to see the citizens as their own family members with this measure and focus, educational benefits for all is possible!

2. PROSPERITY

This is an avenue for government to create employment for all, the leadership can engage, collaborate, and partner with other private organizations within the nation and the international organizations for the creation of more jobs to tackle unemployment that hinders economic instability which leads to poverty, pressures, depression etc., some in the western world and the developing nations find it unreasonable that when they pass through education, the issue of unemployment has made their parents and themselves handicap in economic situation. Therefore, some parents found it as a waste of time to study in higher institutions. If the government make the education free for all in all levels. When jobs are created, once the issue of employment are been solved. There will be financial freedom for the citizens. Many will see the need for a University education.

A. Political Stability

When there are completely peace in the political system. If the changing of the government from one person to another leadership do not interfere with their businesses and contracts, Investors will be attracted from other countries into the nation because they know that their businesses will be secured and protected. This will leads to economic growth and development, social benefits will be easy because of the prosperity enjoyment for all.

B. Economy Stability

When economic is stable, businesses is booming, the climate and business environment are profitable. Imports and Exports are made easier for international trades and market. Tax reduction will help more

industries and international development collaboration both in businesses, labour, organization and education as a whole.

C. Financial Stability

When the exchange rate favour the nation, I mean when the currency is powerful to other countries, this will eventually lead more nations citizens to value your country and migrate for good pastures. The transfer of money internationally into the country should be made flexible because of the huge transactions from international companies, banks and other financial institutions that will fast track the inflow of the international financing projects etc., The government must manage the procedure and procure of the commercial tools to be favourable to the businesses and the business environment.

Loan with no interest or lower interest should be the vision of the government in the management of a nation. This will encourage people to utilize the opportunity in venturing into more businesses both national and international. The Central Bank must make policies with the stakeholders for easy life for the business and the business owners. It will all help the citizens and the nation at large.

D. Tranquility Stability

This has to do with both peace of mind and peaceful environment, this will aid better health and vitality for the purpose of prosperity. There must be a good health system for all for free and availability in every corner of the nation. This will help population growth and reduce pressure, mortality rate, death rate etc., and the total life expectancy will be better as compared to when there are no availability and free healthcare system. More free educational research institute for the medical should be made as regard to this. So that the nation do not experience the shortage of medical personnel. Access to good health, peace of mind, peaceful environment is also to foster prosperity.

3. FACILITY

Facility is the third dimension of these basic need. This deals with the Infrastructures, good road, effective transportation systems and their management. Lights is a major thing that can not be ignored by any reasonable and responsible government because we can not over emphasize how this has a lot of positive effects on the whole nation. For business, individual citizens to enjoy and utilize it at their disposal. Most companies have relocation to another country that their light is constant and affordable. The government must make sure that electric supply has a positive impacts towards the growth of all sectors and social development in any nation.

The Solar Energy

The world is advancing, according to the United Nations 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) towards 2030. The Solar will be the order of the day because of the low carbon emissions that the world is working towards. Now any nations that want to meet up with this standard must embark massively on Solar energy as fast as possible. More awareness should be made in all our educational training institutions and the government should make a provision with subsidy if the need be, to actualized what will help our health concerning the climate change.

The Hospital Free Treatment

This is more than necessary, the government is the hope of the masses because of what is happening in our planet. Citizens health is a serious priority for responsible government and leadership. Everyone should be free to go inside the hospital for treatment of any illness and the delivery of the baby. The treatment, the drugs, and surgery if the need be should all be free to everyone especially the citizens of the nations. The United Kingdom have got the vision of free health many years ago, if not a century. This have help their kingdom, government and their citizens to be loyal and contribute to the development of their nation. Some other nations who their government embrace this free healthcare for all citizens will become a great nation in population and life expectancy because mortality rate will decrease. Is it really free or because the citizens pay National Health Scheme (NHS). Well the payment is a pin nuts as compared to the free treatment, free delivery, free surgery, free drugs etc., So you can see transparency and the commitment of their citizens towards the NHS Scheme.

Education Infastructures

Not just having a quality educational systems but also a good infastructures. The good learning environment that will aid the students assimilation and development in their studies. equipment for research work, in medical, technology, science, education, philosophy, arts, functional libraries etc.

Institutions

The Institutions were connected together for evaluation purposes every year. The funding for research by the government, private organizations and individual are really helping the western world educational institutions. It's time for other nations to begin to do things right for the betterment of their citizens as they see other citizens in other nations enjoying these education facility.

Museums

The museum is a place to see the past, recalled and have in-depth knowledge for leverage and tackle the future in a secure manner. This help the children, the youth and anyone to understand better for

visibility study and exposure on its own. It creates employment also, empowering people's mentality for educational purposes. How many citizens go to the museum? This will give you a clue as to what your people value, this can be traced to the kind of education you have made of them.

Amusement park

A place to walk into and relax yourself for refreshing, meditating, enjoying etc., the money the government spent on this is never in vain but to make their citizens happy and feel they belong to the nation. The parent and family can go there for birthdays, occasions, and celebrations of any kind. It is a sign you are thinking of them as a citizen. Children go there to play. However, there must be security else, the people will not use the amusement parks.

Airports

Anyone coming into the country, the airport speaks a volume of words both to the visitors and the citizens of your country. It gives a clue to the image of your nation, how the people behaved and many other things. For this reason, the government must do wonderful infrastructures in the airport. The diplomatic relations within the government agencies that work in the airport must market the nation for more flights to make full use of the airport. This is an avenue for revenue in service rendered to the citizens of the nation and the citizens of other countries. Many passengers take some flights to see what is happening in the latest development in that country. Dubai is an example when their airport was newly built many people rush into the place to see the massive infrastructures. It was wonderful. Everyone wants to see new innovations and beautiful infrastructures!

Seaports

This is also a great place that shows the image of the nation. Therefore, every government of any nation must invest into the seaports because this also is an entrance to the country for economic growth and international trade businesses. The cargo must be easier and quicker to clear exports and imports. This will make many businesses to use the seaports. Taxes should be reduced for businesses to function properly and you will discover that businessmen will not be importing goods through neighborhood countries as an illegal work. This happens when the seaports and the landboarders are flexible with their structure for easy movement of legal goods that will help the citizens.

Borderlands

The border land should be made easier for goods to flow into the country for economic growth and boost. This will reduce price because the heavy duty pay is not cumbersome. Thus, everyone that has

business to do within that country will find it easier to engage and collaborate with. Government must have a good infrastructure in these borders to make things easier for living and non living things movement.

Free Accommodations for all

It is essential for us as human to have a place to sleep. If the government provides free accommodations, you will see that every landlord will be forced to reduce the price of their house rentals. It is more than necessary that in the management of a nation the government should do their best in making the citizens' burden flexible. The United Kingdom has got the vision. Their kingdom and government have provided free houses for their citizens. What happened to other nations? Why can't they see this vision.

In fact, the government can have more better dreams for their citizens. It was a shameful thing to see a citizen of a country sleep in the streets at night both in some western world and the developing nations. This is serious! The government needs to place more value on humans and animals, properties etc.,

Transportation

Transportation systems are necessary than you can imagine. Land, Air, Sea and underground. I have seen some advanced nations have utilized and maximized their transportation systems. The road, the underground, railroad and the sea, air must be used to reduce congestion. Always remember that the next twenty years more people will be born, more citizens will have more cars, some will buy more private jets, ships, etc., All this should suggest to a well visionary leader and government to involve in massive road constructions, railways, infrastructure, more airports and seaports that will be able to accommodate all with their demands. Else, the government is looking for protests, chaos, changing of his or her government when things that ought to be done are not done.

In view of this, it is essential for the government and the leadership of any nation to be proactive. Looking into the future and plan how to strategize the easiest way of overcoming these unending challenges. All these, if well utilized will be an avenue for revenue to the government.

4. SECURITY

Security of citizens, properties, information, health, futuristic and the population growth are very much important. For this reason, the citizens want secured hope and unfailing assurance from their nations and government. This is a major problem in every nation on this planet earth!

Since the pandemic, the quick response of the intelligent peoples are unbelievable. Due to the lockdown policy to safe the world. This is also a security of life. Many have lost their lives in the civic 19 season. But the government put some measurements in place for us to recover from the epidemic.

More studies were done to resolve,cure and tackle the issues. Each nations gradually have opened their border for businesses to continue as usual. When the citizens discovered that there are not hope in the government of the day in their country they move out of that country some may come back, when things are settled,while some will never come to that nations again because of the standard of living and security purposes.The government must be productive not redundant in nature, that is why the education for all at all levels should be free, this will aid the stakeholders to bring excellent ideas for the formulation of policies by the policymakers through brainstorming period for the nation's development and management of their resources.

Food bank and Food Stability

Agriculture and food are necessary if you want to keep a nation and mange it.citizen we look for survival. You need people for the making of a good nation. The professionals and others have to work with the government for effective governing, that is when the government are ready to listen and take approved suggestions and recommendations.Let food be surplus in the nation.With cheeper rate which must be available and affordable for all.

The Old Age

The older age people must be part of the people we have to take proper care on them. Once every citizens knows there will be a secure provision in their old age. The level of stealing will reduce, pressure af not attain success will be removed. This will make people in that nation to be contempt with a good reasonable percentage. The Elderly should be given allowance to buy things with their pension money. They will in turn share their wisdom to the government through their experiences and regrets in life.

A Secured Employment

Everyone love lo work at least but want a stable, sustainable and a secure work that will be reliable without being sacked or rejected when the employee became sick or depressed.In view of this security of employment. The government should make a policy that the employee citizens will feel secured while working should anything happens, she or he is covered not only by insurance but also by the government of the day. When this secured assurance provisions is in place, you will see the citizens

worker do the job that was being employed for with all total commitment, loyalty and actively stable with the work.

The Population

The matter of security; political, physical, economical, financial, educational, marital etc., will enhance quality life for population growth. People want safety place and nation for their standard of living. Parents want their children to be in a safe environment because no body want loss of lives, property, possession, loss of job etc., We want all our things to be secured including living and non living things. When the government work more on managing the nation for peace, tranquility, hope and safety. It will affect the population positively and the will help to boost economic, value and development. Population can be controlled but under population can be helped for achieving a better results. We can see that example; when President Clinton integrated the visa lottery program, this is to help population growth and the country at large for a leverage in the world generally for people. Many through this medium becoming American Citizens. They live a better life.

More than a Enough Strategy

This more than enough strategy is a way of having surplusity in production of what the masses needs. For example, the nation should create jobs for all unemployed people in their country. Let everyone be engaged in a legal works! This will reduce unemployment rate.

Quarter for example, their airline business was taken seriously to the extent that when you want to go the the United Kingdom from any part of the world, there are more of their airlines that will take you from Doha which is their capital City to Bristol, Liverpool, Manchester, London, Reading etc., all the cities in the same UK, what a wonderful works, this is what am saying; there should be more of choices, and options if indeed we want to meet the needs of the common person as a nation. The government of each nations must be creating, producing, employing and doing more than enough in the supply of goods and services for their citizens in all ramifications to meet their needs as a family members bond by the same blood. This will help the citizens to understand what direction the government and it's leadership are taking them to in the future. It will avoid protests, chaos and wars within the nation and outside when many things are put into serious consideration. More than enough food, industries, vehicles, houses, tangible and intangible things, all for the benefits of all.

Furthermore, on the issue of the basic needs and it's four dimensions which government must take heed to, as a responsible leadership are; mentality, that deals with the education of the citizens minds and this must be free in all levels from primary to university. The second is the Prosperity, which deals with the peace, tranquility, and economic stability, financial freedom and businesses in the nation, so government must maintain the peaceful environment for growth and development to take it's place.

Thirdly, is the facility, that meant the Infrastructures, good roads and effective transportation systems. This means doing exceptional things that will attract other nations to your country. Finally, is the fourth one, that deals with security, because without it, there will be chaos, the security have to be in all areas, sectors for the citizens to have physical rest of mind, emotional, economical, educational, futuristical etc., Security should be properly taken care of, for the citizens future sake, if the government do not want to waste their people's lives in wars, hunger, abject poverty, unemployment, illegal works, chaos, unresolved damages and trauma of any kind of regrets, hopelessness etc.,

Technology and Information

There must be security for everyone's information. With the use of technology and its gadgets it's necessary that the security must be well managed in every financial institutions, personal datas, although, there should be access to information on educational purposes, verification purpose, background checks for employment purpose etc., In the mist of these there must be a secured technology system to aid this measures.

PRACTICAL WAYS TO THE MANAGEMENT OF A NATION

Managing the people's lives

The lives of the people or the citizens of any nation must be valuable to the extent that the government should make them to be comfortable at all cost. If the leadership value their lives, the leader will do what will bring benefits to them. The live of the individual from children to adults should be very precious to the leadership of any country. This will persuade the leader to work in a team with others for effectiveness and productiveness. The people are what makes a nation. Therefore, without them the nation do not exist. Why shouldn't the government place more priority to the welfares of the people in all aspects of their lives, and as such they will be willing to stay in their nations by settlement, contribution to the development of the nation because they were happy. Thus, the citizens will be united and work together. If they are not well treated, most of them will migrate to other nations that can care for their lives better.

Managing the population growth

The population is a great factor that show honour, glory and power. This is one of the major reason why nations do not want division or separation into smaller countries. However, when there are issues that are not resolved and solved, everyone will fight to go their own way. Of course, people want freedom,

honour, fulfillment and development. When the government avoid protests, chaos and wars through taking proper care on the citizens. More people will migrate into their nations. Everyone wants survival and will do their best to achieve that despite the challenges, the risks, threats etc., It is very much essential to manage the population. You can see in the United States of America, that each States have their own laws to govern their states. This shows you that the citizens are not comfortable in some states. Thus, move to another States that they can adapt to the State's law, else the country would have break up into many nations; that is an example of how to manage a nation. This have help their population management and development by offering visa lottery program. This cause many people to migrate into their country.

Managing their resources; natural, human capital, financial etc.,

When the government fails to deliver for the people what they want to see. What will be afterward is protests, unhappiness, chaos etc., It is essential to identifying, utilizing and maximizing the resources of any nation effectively. The world have turn to a global village and every citizens that are conversant with the latest development and management of things that is happening in other countries will be furious with their government with her leadership because everyone want to see new things as compared and contrasted to other nations in the world. This is the 21centry challenges for every government. The natural resources from God should be well identified, utilized and maximized these will bring revenues for the government to plan on to engage in infrastructures, education, transportation, businesses; locally and Internationally for empowerments. The human capital may migrate to other nations that could appreciate them so that they will not be under utilized and under pay as compared to their counterpart in other countries. It is more than necessary for the developing nations to wake up to their able duties and work for the betterment of their citizens. people want prosperity not austerity! A leader must find ways for solutions that is why the capitalists, professionals, business gurus should be called upon constantly for advise but there must be transparency and national interest for it to work.

Managing their economy

The management of economy goes a longer way because it's a determine factor for the nation to go forward or backward in their GDP based on their economy growths and stability. This is what will make the citizens to stay within the country or some may flee into other nations for businesses, settlement, advancement and achievement. The exports should be more than the imports, this is a good deal for the international trade and it boost the economy growth. However, if the importations are more than what is being exported outside the country, this leads to market dropping in the international communities. For this reasons, taxes must be control to favour domestic industries, lower interest rate or no interest at all for the local company to be encouraged. It will create employment, the government should collaborate with both national and international organizations for economical development through

partnership. This will attract international investors and financial transactions will help the nation for international exchange rate.

Managing the environment and the environmental protection

The environment and the systems of the nation need to be managed properly to favour education, inventory, businesses, political stability, security etc., To what level does the environment integrate an international investment, can a locally made product compete with international products? The environment should be friendly for new avenues for revenue and development with infrastructures. How do we welcome new ideas? Do the government implement recommendations through research studies or dictatorship is the order of the day? If in deed, we want to manage the environment within and the environment without; which is the image of the nation to the international communities. We have to follow what will help our environment and support the green for climate safety. The environment must be protected both naturally and artificially. This is essential if we want the management of the nation to become a reality without protests, chaos and wars.

Managing the culture

Each nation with their uniqueness and culture. It is vital to embrace the positive culture so that you will be cultured. You don't throw away your unique identity else you are nowhere to be found. Some nations have lost their cultural life, The leadership of the government must reserve the cultural heritage for the next generation to be able to see and know their values. In some nations tourism is a huge and big business because their government invest into it. Innovations, modifications and glorifications are being applied to the culture to fit into the civilization for revenues. With critical thinking and working, more gains will be realized both in the art and culture of the nation by the government and the citizens. Culture has to do with a lot of things, the behavioural ways of the citizens lives, communication, how they understand things, their beliefs system and general philosophy, all are inclusive to their management.

Managing the electoral process

The electoral process is a vital point in the totality of the leadership of the nation and government. How transparent it is, can give a clue to how the government and the nation will be governed and managed by the government of the day. For this reason, it is important that the procedures and processes of elections, the leadership requirements and qualifications will aid to the development of the nation. The structure of the system of appointments, election, vote and counting strategy have a great impact on how the management of the nation will be in order to avoid protests, chaos and wars. The simplicity of the whole electoral process from the recruitment to the announcement of winners have a lot of implications either positive or negative.

Managing and maintaining the Infrastructures and the sustainability

The Infrastructures cost a huge amount of money, this must be sustained and maintained. The government must be cautious of the ways and manners they approach their citizens because the government is supposed to be a servant leader; who listening, engaging and show the citizens by a good example that can be followed. Else, the Infrastructures could end up been destroyed when there are violent protests, chaos and wars. Many beautiful infrastructures have been destroyed in many places where war, violence, protests, chaos, natural disasters etc., The first World war, the second World war, Syria etc., have not yet recovered form the traumatic experience, costs and the consequences. This is why some countries invest into ammunitions, war weapons, etc., So that nations do not attacked them due to their sophisticated weapons. However, the civil war; which is a war within could occur if care is not taken. Right from the injustice to protests, things can escalate which will invariably lead to serious violence and war. In view of this, why can't the government avoid it, in the cause of management of the nation. If the government see the citizens as their nuclear family members, we would not need the nuclear weapons both national and international because we are part of the United Nations.

Managing the right productive and effective systems

It is important to be productive and effective, especially, if the system is in place. If not you as a leader must fine a way of having a productive and effective systems in your government for your citizens. This will help your administration, management, development and stability of all that is needed in the nation; towards better economic growth, social amenities, education, political stability and security measures in every sector and section of the nation government.

Managing the currency power and the rate to other currency in other nations

The currency determine the flow of current of people to migrate to the most powerful currency in the world. The power of what your nation current can buy in the international market for international trades and exchange will determine a lot of your strength as a government and nation. Therefore, it's a must to emback on development in business, exports, education and massive support to the local industries.

Managing the government and the structures

The mismanagement of the government and her structure will definitely leads to corruption of characters, resources, power abuse, inequality, debts, no external reserve for the nation and lack of transparent systems in every sector and section. There should be a strategical methods of policies, structures and systems in place that we help the citizens, the leadership of the government and it's agencies for easy flow with one another in their different agencies.

Managing the reserve with caution

The stealing of the reserve or the mismanagement of the reserve money will collapse the nation economic value. Loaning habit from the World Bank and the International Monetary Fund (IMF) will cause the national currency exchange to be weaken and worse. These are the major reasons why the government and their leadership must endeavour to manage the reserve with caution.

Managing visionary leader with quality character

Every visionary leader that is being discovered by the nation should be managed so that those visionary leader do not loose interest in the government and the leadership of the nation. The qualitative character of such fellow and people like them will be under utilized or the unqualified took over the government of the nation through some manipulation. This also affect the nation one way and the other. We can trace the major problem of different nations to the bad people in government and their selfish interest.

Getting leaders and managers that have love for the masses

The need to look critically for the kind of leaders who have the love for the masses at heart is a major challenges in this present world. Most nations have leaders from the godfathers who have being recycling themselves in the government arena and corridors of power. Therefore, the same philosophical methods are being used over and over again. Are we sure that the people adaptation is not depression where by looking for an opportunity to strike, protests violently, opposing when the right time comes. The leadership must be mindful of their citizens needs, this will be of a great help but when the government are depriving her people their rights, benefits, happiness, freedom and honour. It will make them to dishonour the leadership if not in their presence but in their absence. Every nation on earth needs a government that has serious passion for the citizens to meet all their needs.

Getting Team that leads without biases

The government and her agencies should work as a team without biases. This will help the citizens to trust them more for transparent system that will be effective in performance. All activities within the agencies must be a team work. so that when another government is in power, performance will be effective without any delay of any kind in their duties.

Managing the foreigners

All the foreigners must be managed properly for security, economic, business and population wise. The best can be derived from the foreigners if well utilized. Hardly will you see a nation without a foreigner because people venture, traveling into different countries for various reasons. To some, to see new people culture, for businesses, tourism, education, exposure, enlightenment, research work, knowing new places etc., Thus, unlimited revenues can enter into the government purse and the citizens for economic boost.

THE CONCLUSION

The management of a nation; avoiding protests, chaos and wars is the solution when there are willingness to pursuing what will benefit all, than personal interest by consulting all the citizens because they are part of the nation and government. This will be a serious solution to most of the world's problems. The removal of personal interest by the leadership in government but to embrace national interest, not the cabals who are after their own pockets at the expenses of the masses discomfort. The nation want the capitalist, the professionals, and businesses that have societal development corporate benefits for all to boost the nation's image in the international communities.

THE PARADIGM SHIFT IS NOW!

The paradigm shift from ruling a nation to serving the nation for development, sustainment, management and the benefits WELFARE for all the citizens towards national interest as a member of one family. This should be the major goal of every nations that will be a leading champion in the world now. No more champion of the world through winning of wars, nuclear, armunitions but we want to know the champions nations through how you are caring for your citizens with all pleasure among the pressures we are all facing in the world.

Summary

The summary of this whole texts for us to understand that we need to place more values on lives of the citizens, they are the bond family members with the government and her leadership. Therefore, the total management of the people from children to youths, women, men and the elderly people, should be catered for than what has been done. It's high time each citizens should know they are part of the nation through the engagement of outstanding benefits in every aspects of their lives. This will stop a lot of crimes, protests, chaos and wars. It's time to avoid all these because the over load work of the United Nations is cumbersome, I do not know how in reality, the United Nations will achieved the 17 Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) towards 2030. We have 8 years to meet the target!

Meanwhile, many nations among the 187 membership states have not yet solve the equation of administration and distribution of social developmental package. Like free educational, free and fair election, mass employment, financial stability, free clean water for all, gender equality and true freedom of human rights among many others. In addition, if the government take good care of the citizens and their standard of living. Each nation will have avoid protests, chaos and wars.

Suggestions

In my suggestions, let's the government give allowance to the elderly people in the nation, they have pass through various experiences and they would become great advisers to the government and leadership.

The unemployed women,men and youths should be given allowances for their upkeeping.

Anyone that want to married should be helped financial and in free accomodations for all,this will reduce the rate of divorce in the society, this was done in Libya and now in UAE.

Free Accomodations for every citizens that do not have shelter,this is happening in the United Kingdom and in some of the western world countries.

Free Treatment, Drugs, Surgery,etc., this is happening in United Kingdom,UAE, and the European Union etc.,

Free Education for all from Primary to the University in all levels to postgraduate.This is happening in the European Union. This will encourage people to learn and go to the higher institutions if they have no fund or employment parents.

Free Funeral for the elderly and free Healthcare workers for them, this is happening in UAE.This will make the elders to live longer. Their burdens will not kill their children who had no funds to care for their parents. This will safe everyone from pressure that cause many to engage in illegal activities in order to get money.

Fee loan with no interest or lower interest rate. This will bring empowerment for individual citizens to emback on business that they love to do. This will safe the adult from frustrations that make most to leave the family; spouse, children because they couldn't meet up with their financial obligations.

The stakeholders and all the citizens should be engaged with rightful information before designing any policy by the policymakers.

Recommendations

I recommend this writing to everyone in a leadership position in the government to read and to implement these words and concepts. Thus, it will help in the management of their nations for avoidance of protests, chaos and wars. Without using a forceful method strategy; the police and the military.

